

Studies on the Influence of Some Supporting Electrolytes on the Diffusion Current and Half-wave Potential of the Reducible Ions. Part II. Polarographic Reduction of Cd^{2+} Ions

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The variations in the diffusion current (i_d) and half-wave potential ($E_{1/2}$) have been studied in the polarographic reduction of Cd^{2+} in $CdCl_2$ and $Cd(NO_3)_2$ with different concentrations of several supporting electrolytes. On increasing the concentration of the supporting electrolyte, the interfacial tension has been found to fall with the consequent increase in adsorption at the mercury-solution interface with the acetates of Na, Zn, Mg, and Sr. The order of decrease in i_d is more or less in correspondence with the fall in the interfacial tension. On the contrary, the interfacial tension of the oxalates of Na, K, and NH_4 at the mercury surface is increased by raising their concentration, as also the i_d values of the reducible Cd^{2+} system.

That the variation in interfacial tension and adsorption with the varied concentrations of supporting electrolyte in the polarographic reduction of Cd^{2+} ions influences the validity of Ilkovic's equation has already been reported¹. Earlier workers ascribed such small variations in diffusion current and half-wave potential to several factors, such as effective diffusion and activity coefficients², ionic strength³, stirring effect⁴, viscosity, complex formation, interionic attraction, overvoltage⁵, etc.

Interfacial tension, ionic strength, and adsorption⁶ are also known to affect i_d and $E_{1/2}$ in the polarographic reduction processes. The influence of the foregoing factors in the reduction of Cd^{2+} ions by dropping mercury electrode has been investigated in the present communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

Lange's polarometer was used to measure the diffusion current in conjunction with the saturated calomel electrode, which was connected to the solution cell through the salt bridge of saturated NH_4NO_3 in order to nullify the effect of liquid-junction potential. Hydrogen gas (Meites⁷) was bubbled to deoxygenate the solution. Drop time was maintained at 3 sec./drop. 0.02% Gelatin was used as a maximum suppressor. The ionic strength, $\frac{1}{2}ECZ^2$, was obtained by calculation.

1. Nath and Bhattacharya, *this Journal*, 1963, **40**, 253.
2. Lingane and Kolthoff, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **61**, 1045.
3. Ford and Anderson, *ibid.*, 1950, **72**, 3918.
4. MacNevin and Balis, *ibid.*, 1943, **65**, 680.
5. Mukherjee and Chakravarti, *this Journal*, 1961, **38**, 955; 1962, **39**, 181.
6. Reilly and Stumm, U. S. Dept. Com. Office tech. Serv. PB. Report, 1959, **44**, 144283.
7. "Polarographic Techniques", p. 33, Interscience Publishers, N. Y., 1955.

The interfacial tensions between mercury and the different solutions of the supporting electrolyte of varied concentrations in the reducible CdCl_2 and $\text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ systems were determined by the capillary method, as recommended by Bartell *et al.*⁸. The interfacial tension (σ_i) is obtained from the relation:

$$\sigma_i = \frac{rg}{2} (h' d' - h'' d'')$$

where r is the radius of the capillary, d' and d'' , are the densities of mercury and the solution respectively; h' and h'' are the heights of mercury and solution column, respectively, above the mercury-solution interface.

TABLE I

Cd^{2+} as the reducing ion in CdCl_2 soln.

Conc.	A. Na-acetate as supporting electrolyte.					B. Zn-acetate as supporting electrolyte.				
	i_d	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$	σ_i (dynes/ cm).	ΓRT	μ	i_d	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$	σ_i (dynes/ cm).	ΓRT	μ
<i>M/100</i>	8.84 μA	0.575 volt	401.95	..	0.013	9.34 μA	0.585 volt	400.60	..	0.033
<i>M/25</i>	8.66	0.585	391.28	17.720	0.043	9.16	0.585	397.40	15.280	0.123
<i>M/10</i>	8.46	0.595	387.24	10.160	0.103	7.92	0.590	392.37	12.650	0.303
<i>M/2</i>	8.10	0.600	383.40	5.408	0.503	7.00	0.605	385.44	9.913	1.503
<i>M</i>	7.92	0.625	382.82	2.125	1.003	6.26	0.610	384.20	4.119	3.063
	C. Mg-acetate as supporting electrolyte.					D. Sr-acetate as supporting electrolyte.				
<i>M/100</i>	10.13	0.585	419.44	..	0.033	10.31	0.585	405.03	..	0.033
<i>M/25</i>	9.34	0.590	411.87	12.570	0.123	9.34	0.590	401.04	8.627	0.123
<i>M/10</i>	9.16	0.595	408.56	8.322	0.303	8.42	0.595	398.78	5.882	0.303
<i>M/2</i>	7.92	0.615	404.48	5.865	1.503	7.92	0.625	397.75	1.473	1.503
<i>M</i>	6.82	0.620	402.90	5.181	3.003	6.26	0.635	..	..	3.003

TABLE II

Cd^{2+} as the reducing ion in the $\text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ soln.

Conc.	A. Na-acetate as supporting electrolyte.					B. Zn-acetate as supporting electrolyte.				
	i_d	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$	σ_i (dynes/ cm).	ΓRT	μ	i_d	$E_{\frac{1}{2}}$	σ_i (dynes/ cm).	ΓRT	μ
<i>M/100</i>	9.16 μA	0.580 volt	402.85	..	0.013	9.57 μA	0.585 volt	410.2	..	0.033
<i>M/25</i>	9.00	0.585	392.14	17.29	0.043	9.40	0.590	400.5	16.110	0.123
<i>M/10</i>	8.46	0.600	386.50	14.18	0.103	9.00	0.595	396.3	10.550	0.303
<i>M/2</i>	7.92	0.620	381.44	7.24	0.503	7.72	0.600	390.4	8.149	1.503
<i>M</i>	7.37	0.630	380.04	4.65	1.003	7.37	0.610	389.0	3.656	3.005
	C. Mg-acetate as supporting electrolyte.					D. Sr-acetate as supporting electrolyte.				
<i>M/100</i>	9.76	0.580	425.4	..	0.033	9.76	0.580	407.0	..	0.033
<i>M/25</i>	9.21	0.585	417.2	13.610	0.123	9.34	0.585	400.7	10.460	0.123
<i>M/10</i>	8.47	0.590	413.4	9.552	0.303	9.16	0.595	397.4	8.286	0.303
<i>M/2</i>	7.37	0.610	410.6	4.005	1.503	7.00	0.625	394.4	4.291	1.503
<i>M</i>	7.00	0.630	409.5	3.655	3.005	6.06	0.635	392.2	3.955	3.005

8. Bartell, *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 2419.

TABLE II (contd.)

E. Na-oxalate as supporting electrolyte.						F. K-oxalate as supporting electrolyte.				
Conc.	i_d	$E_{1/2}$	σ_i (dynes/cm).	ΓRT	μ	i_d	$E_{1/2}$	σ_i (dynes/cm).	ΓRT	μ
<i>M</i> /200	5.90 μ a	0.605 volt	397.4	..	0.026	6.08 μ a	0.610 volt	389.2	..	0.026
<i>M</i> /100	6.26	0.610	402.2	-24.00	0.046	6.65	0.620	394.3	-25.44	0.046
<i>M</i> /50	6.90	0.620	406.0	-10.00	0.086	7.00	0.630	398.2	-19.50	0.086
<i>M</i> /25	7.37	0.635	408.3	-11.52	0.160	7.75	0.640	410.8	-13.00	0.166
<i>M</i> /10	7.92	0.650	410.4	-10.58	0.406	8.10	0.665	413.2	-12.90	0.406
G. NH ₄ oxalate as supporting electrolyte.										
<i>M</i> /200	5.54	0.600	382.4	..	0.026					
<i>M</i> /100	6.08	0.615	387.0	-23.00	0.046					
<i>M</i> /50	6.53	0.625	401.0	-20.01	0.086					
<i>M</i> /25	7.18	0.640	403.5	-12.50	0.166					
<i>M</i> /10	7.37	0.655	405.5	-10.23	0.406					

DISCUSSION

According to the Gibbs adsorption equation, lowering of interfacial tension (σ_i) relates to positive adsorption, whereas a rise in interfacial tension indicates that the concentration of the adsorbed substance at the surface would be gradually less with increasing concentration of the electrolyte added—the so-called negative adsorptions. This seems to be a very relevant factor with respect to the behaviour of the dropping mercury electrode with the supporting electrolyte ranging from low to high concentrations. Table I and Table II (A-D) show that the values of i_d and $E_{1/2}$ are not exactly identical for the chloride and nitrate solutions of Cd. This suggests that the i_d and $E_{1/2}$ are not only the function of the nature of the reducible ion and the supporting electrolyte used, but also depend on the anion of the reducible cation. By comparing the variations in i_d and $E_{1/2}$ with Na-acetate and Na-oxalate as supporting electrolytes (vide Tables IA & IIA, E), the diffusion currents are found appreciably lower with the oxalates than with the acetates. This is a significant observation, which needs explanation on further study.

Since the inorganic cations are capillary-inactive, it is more probable that the acetate and oxalate ions of the supporting electrolyte are responsible for lowering or raising the interfacial tension at the d.m.e. These anions are positively or negatively adsorbed according to the Gibbs equation. The diffusion current as well as the σ_i suffers a lowering (positive adsorption) with the increase in the concentration c_s of the supporting electrolyte (acetate), but the reverse is the case with oxalates of Na⁺, K⁺, and NH₄⁺, where there is a negative adsorption (Table II E-G).

It is also known that the effective pressure of mercury P_{eff} :

$$P_{\text{eff}} = \propto \frac{1}{\sigma_i} \cdot \propto \frac{1}{t}$$

where σ_i is the interfacial tension and t is the drop-time. Thus t is proportional to σ_i , which means that t corresponds to the rise or fall in the interfacial tension of the supporting electrolyte at the mercury surface, although it is supposed that $m^{2/3} t^{1/6}$

remains practically constant in Ilkovic's equation to ensure constant values of i_d . Since σ_i is closely connected with adsorption, changes in i_d may be also connected with ΓRT , which may be interpreted from its dimensions as the rate of change of adsorption per unit time with change of concentration, and is intimately connected with the state of saturation of the mercury drop with respect to the adsorbed substances.

The amount adsorbed may also be regarded as a function of concentration or ionic strength of the supporting electrolyte from which it follows that the concept of ionic strength and adsorption can be interlinked to explain the variations in the value of i_d and E_1 . It is well known that surface-active substances even in traces influence the electrode process and so our observations bring out a definite evidence in treating the adsorption phenomenon as one of considerable significance, among other parameters, to explain the divergence from Ilkovic's equation. Further work is in progress.

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